

THE PROBLEM OF WILL AND VOLUNTARILY QUALITIES IN THE WORKS OF EASTERN ARTISTS

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The encyclopedic scientists of the East have given a number of scientific-theoretical opinions on personal training, education, personal development and formation of moral skills. Also, a number of opinions have been put forward regarding the role of will and volitional qualities in personality development. Among them, we should mention our scholars such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Jami, Davani, Alisher Nawai.

In the "Qur'an" much attention is paid to patience as a high moral virtue. Therefore, patience is the most mentioned moral quality in the Qur'an. The Qur'an teaches that patience perfects the following qualities in a person. For example, courage is manifested as a result of patience in difficulties, chastity is the patience of sexual feelings, meekness is interpreted as a criterion of patience.

If you persevere, you will fear Allah (you will be saved), as stated in the "Qur'an", it is shown that patience consists of enduring these difficulties, enduring injustices caused by bad people, and enduring adversity. Adhering to these factors will end difficulties in a person and will not bow down in front of adversity. And this is considered the highest quality of a person [2].

Farabi says that before starting the work of education, one should know the personal characteristics of people. According to him, it is necessary to know the characteristics of desire in a person, such as free will, good and bad. In his opinion, starting a job without determining what a person is willing to do and what he is capable of will not give the expected result [3].

According to Ibn Sina, morality is not innate, it is formed through education. The goal of moral education, according to the scientist, is to cultivate a person who lives not only for his own benefit, but also for others. In order to realize this goal, young people should develop humanity, true friendship, correctness, strong will, and faith [3].

According to the teachings of Kubroviya, it is said that a person should rely on the following ten principles to achieve perfection. The most important of them include the following; the fourth basis is satisfaction, which in its essence is determined by; contentment with the little things that make life content, turning away from all the pleasures and lusts that attract one's self, eating too much food, coveting expensive clothes, entertainment, idleness, etc.

The eighth principle is to be patient and voluntarily withdraw from the sphere of the ego even if it is suffering. In order not to go astray from the accepted right path, a person must suppress his inclinations. Its purpose is that the heart should be cleansed from the powers, and the soul should be restrained if it is corrupted by lust [2].

Omar Khayyam's excessive demands on himself and people were expressed in the rules he developed about the need to educate a person from childhood and throughout his life. According to Umar Khayyam, a person who combines intelligence with knowledge and behavior and determination to do good to all people is such a perfect person in terms of all practical and theoretical qualities [3].

Davani considered courage and bravery to be one of the positive qualities of a person. He understands that it is very necessary for young people to acquire this understanding. He understands ambition in a broad sense. Courage includes humility, gentleness, bravery, perseverance, endurance and other qualities.

Davani sees courage as a concept that evaluates a person's behavior and relationships with others. He says that if a person is faced with any danger, he should hold himself firmly, not to be restless, to be persistent, not to be forced by failures, to be persistent, and he calls such behavior as ambition.

Davani believed that courage should be subordinated to a person's reason: "courage happens at the behest of the mind, it becomes real only when its goal is to acquire (positive) qualities". So, according to him, whenever a person acts impulsively, it must be based on the command and necessity of the mind.

According to the thinker, one can see signs of passion in animals as well. But this enthusiasm is completely different from true enthusiasm. The way of life of animals is instinctive and not based on reason. Because they have no intelligence.

Davani considered the soldiers to be the bravest, bravest people because they guard the state border. That is why they are the most trusted people of the state. It is considered necessary for the king to provide them with all-round support and financial assistance. According to Davani, some people do things that look like courage and bravery from the outside. They do such activities out of greed for personal gain to achieve their own selfish goals. Such mischief can never be classified as passion. He contrasts cowardice with ambition. Some people avoid difficulties and think of a way to live an easy life. Davani considers such people to be heartless and infamous and criticizes them harshly.

He considers the concept of contentment to be a good quality of the human spirit. Most importantly, he linked satisfaction with necessary behaviors. A person should act only on the basis of necessity. In the world, a person needs only the most necessary things, there is no need to strive for others. For example, knowing the limits in eating, drinking, emotional and other behaviors, observing moderation, norms, especially not wanting wealth means satisfaction [1].

From the above points, it can be seen that in the development of a person, in addition to education and formation of behavioral norms, it is important to form voluntary qualities. Therefore, the program serves the purpose of educating mature, strong-willed, and patient individuals from the scientific heritage left by our scholars.

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